

DAMAGE AND PLASTICITY IN METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES: IMPLICATIONS ON CONSTITUTIVE AND LIFE MODELING

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ABSTRACT

Inelastic deformation mechanisms in SCS-6/Ti 15-3 metal matrix composites consist of both damage and plasticity. Role of damage and plasticity are assessed in relation to the constitutive response in monotonic tension and compression. Several constitutive models are evaluated and their strength and weaknesses are pointed out. Also, it is observed that the inelastic deformation mechanisms under fatigue loading are quite different than observed in monotonic loading and requires special attention in life modeling.

KEYWORDS: Damage, Plasticity, Metal Matrix Composites, Constitutive Model

1. INTRODUCTION

For composite structural applications including design, knowledge of constitutive response of composite materials is essential to conduct appropriate structural analyses. Constitutive models are like transfer functions which relate global deformation and loading to local deformation and stresses. Their need in computational analyses need not be overemphasized. In high temperature metal matrix composites (MMCs), the constitutive response is confounded, particularly in the nonlinear regime, by a combination of plasticity and damage such as reaction-zone cracks, fiber-matrix debonding, matrix cracking, etc. This issue has been extensively addressed by the present authors [1-4]. Considerable research to date has been conducted [1-9] to characterize the response of silicon fiber reinforced titanium based composites, such as SCS-6/Ti 15-3 composites.

Often damage accumulates in local regions in a structure due to high stresses and strains. If the damage reaches a critical level, it can lead to failure of the structure. Constitutive models are essential to evaluate local stress and strain fields developed due to global structural loading. However, rational constitutive models can be only developed if the mechanisms for material deformation and damage development can be clarified and used to develop the models. Analytical constitutive models often require an assumption of ideal microstructures and may simplify the problem to a level where realism is compromised, particularly for heterogeneous materials like composites. A computational framework on the other hand provides much versatility and can be effectively utilized provided deformation mechanisms are properly accounted for. For MMC structures subjected to compressive loading (a situation which exists even in the case of

simple bending), constitutive modeling under compressive loading is a clearly defined need and should be considered in parallel with tension loading. Clarification of damage modes and deformation mechanisms are equally important compared with constitutive modeling and are integrally related. The material deformation characteristics and modeling for monotonic loading constitutes the basic requirements for structural analysis.

Inelastic deformation is critical in that its initiation and evolution contributes to the failure of a structural part. Proper constitutive models can only be developed when actual inelastic deformation mechanisms can be ascertained and incorporated into modeling.

In this paper, the deformation mechanism under tensile and compressive loading are presented and they are then related to the constitutive response. Furthermore, a few constitutive models are considered to check their usefulness to predict the constitutive response of this class of materials. The three models which are under consideration are (1) a continuum plasticity based model proposed by Dvorak, et al [10], (2) a micromechanics based computational model proposed by Chamis, et al [11], (3) a 2-D generalized plain strain finite element based Unit Cell Model utilized by Brust, et al [12].

Deformation mechanisms under fatigue loading are addressed as well. The differences in inelastic deformation mechanisms in monotonic and fatigue loading are pointed out. The use of the constitutive models to predict the cyclic behavior and their implications on life modeling are forwarded.

2. ANALYTICAL CONSIDERATIONS

2.1 Vanishing Diameter Fiber (VDF) Model: AGLPLY

Metal matrix composites reinforced by continuous elastic fibers may experience an appreciable amount of elastic-plastic deformation which is caused by plastic flow of the matrix. Nonlinearity in the stress-strain curve has been often associated with matrix plasticity and therefore, continuum plasticity theories have been developed to predict elastic-plastic response of composites. Once such model has been the Vanishing Fiber Diameter (VFD) model which utilizes a mises-type matrix obeying Prager-Ziegler kinematic hardening rule [10].

The material model mentioned above, by virtue of the assumption that the fibers have a vanishing small diameter, offers certain advantages which are essential in the development of plasticity theories of fibrous materials. The most important feature is the existence of uniform strain fields in the constituent phases. As a result, one can derive analytical expressions for overall compliance of the aggregate in terms of the local properties and volume fractions of the phases. Extensions of the model can be made with other hardening rules. These advantages are balanced against other considerations such as the accuracy of the overall response predicted by the model-typically underestimating elastic moduli of the composite. Of greater concern is the behavior in the plastic range, namely, the low-constraint hardening rules in the transverse direction at high fiber concentrations. These aspects of the model predictions indicate that applications of the theory should prefer materials with low to moderate fiber densities, and stress states with low isotropic components. The model typically overestimates fiber stresses. In a way, this is encouraging since additional margin of safety is attained in strength calculations.

From a physical standpoint, assumption of a vanishing diameter fiber appears to be more acceptable in materials reinforced by very small diameter fibers such as FP alumina or T-50 graphite fibers, which have diameters equal to 20 μm and 1.25 μm respectively. In contrast, the

boron and SiC filaments have diameters of about 140 μm , and usually forms monolayers in MMC laminates.

It is anticipated that presence of significant plastic deformation dominating the nonlinear response as in the case of unidirectional MMCs such as $[0]_8$ SCS-6/Ti 15-3 lamina is amenable to AGLPLY analysis, although physical requirements of microstructure such as fiber dimension in these composites are not met. However, when fiber-matrix debonding (damage) is an important failure mode including matrix plastic deformation as in the transverse lamina case, pure plasticity based model such as the VDF model cannot be fully relied upon.

2.2. Thermoviscoplastic Nonlinear Constitutive Relationships for Structural Analysis of High Temperature Metal Matrix Composites

A computational procedure was developed at NASA-Lewis Research Center [11] to predict the response of MMCs which consists of mathematical models which formally and explicitly relate the dependence of constituent material properties on (1) temperature, (2) stress, and (3) time. These mathematical models are collectively called thermoviscoplastic nonlinear constitutive relationships (TVP-NCR). NASA has developed this into a code called METCAN.

The TVP-NCRs are simplified relationship which are computationally effective and relatively easy to use to predict thermal and mechanical response of MMCs. Evaluation of the exponents require matching experimental data. A disadvantage of the modeling approach is that it does not account for the actual physical damage process in the material and that the nonlinear expressions are not justified via observation or physical evidence.

2.3. Finite Element Analysis (FEA): Unit Cell Model

The analytical aspects that were involved in the Unit-Cell FEA model of Brust, et al [12] model are (1) 2-D generalized plane-strain conditions, (2) periodic boundary conditions, (3) classical thermal plasticity for the matrix, whose property was assumed to be independent of position, (4) thermo-elastic properties of the fiber, (5) fiber-matrix interface was modeled as a discrete interface.

3. EXPERIMENTAL ASPECTS

The material tested was an 8-ply unidirectional SCS-6/Ti 15-3 composite, approximately 1.99-mm thick, with a fiber volume fraction of approximately 0.35. The SCS-6 (SiC) fiber diameter is approximately 140 μm , and it contains alternating outer layers of C and Si, which protect the fiber from damage during handling. The Ti 15-3 alloy is a metastable body centered cubic (bcc) beta Ti-alloy, the bcc phase being stabilized by V. The material is metastable because hexagonal close packed (hcp) alpha phase, which is the stable room temperature phase of pure Ti, precipitates when the material is held at temperatures as low as 400°C for long periods of time.

Details of specific tensile, compressive and fatigue testing and specimen dimension can be found in the references [2,3,12] in the same order. Details of microstructural information obtained in the above references are not repeated here. Extensive polishing and replication were conducted as well and are described in those references.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Deformation and failure characteristics obtained via microstructural evaluation under monotonic tensile loading are summarized in Tables 1 and 2.

Figures 1 and 2 are representative photomicrographs which show the key deformation characteristics for the $[0]_8$ and $[90]_8$ lamina under monotonic tensile loading.

Based on the detailed understanding of the deformation characteristics, it appears that matrix plasticity and fiber-matrix debonding are key characteristics for the $[0]_8$ and $[90]_8$ laminae, respectively. As a consequence, the AGLPLY and the Unit Cell FEA models are well suited to predict the constitutive response of these composites as shown in Figures 3 and 4. The METCAN code is also able to provide fairly good match to the experimental data. However, the basis for accounting for the true nonlinearity in the material is somewhat different in that METCAN only simulates the actual processes through computational scheme and constituent property matching (e.g. debonding is simulated using zero stiffness of the interphase).

Microstructural evaluation under monotonic compression for the $[0]_8$ and $[90]_8$ laminae had many interesting characteristics [2]. For brevity, only $[90]_8$ characteristics are summarized in this paper.

Key mechanisms in $[90]_8$ lamina under compression (Table 3) appear to be radial fiber cracking and extensive debonding (Figure 5) [13]. Parallel orientation of these damage modes with respect to loading does not affect the compliance response during unloading. It appears the Unit Cell Model can capture the constitutive response under compression. These results are shown in Figure 6. METCAN and AGLPLY also predict the response fairly well [2]. However, the physics of the deformation is only artificially simulated using these code.

In stress-controlled fatigue of $[0]_8$ lamina, the inelastic deformation mechanisms can be classified as described in Table 4. Considerable information on fatigue mechanisms are forwarded by the authors in [14].

It is clear that a dominant damage mechanism in fatigue is debonding damage (Figure 7) for $[0]_8$ lamina, although matrix cracking is observed in intermediate life range [14]. Long debonds are not common under monotonic tension loading. This change in damage mechanism requires additional consideration for cyclic loading-unloading response. Incorporation into existing constitutive models will be a necessity to predict life of this class of composite materials. At this time, it appears that the physical aspects of this damage mode can be best addressed via 3-D Unit Cell FEA modeling scheme. AGLPLY is unsuitable for addressing any damage and can only address plasticity. METCAN is unsuitable to account for unloading response and can be computationally exhaustive.

An important observation that can be made about the damage process in composites is that unlike metals, a multitude of damage modes affect life as shown in Figure 8. Modeling fatigue damage growth rate in this class of composites is further complicated by the fact that inelastic deformation mechanism is influenced by both damage and plasticity. Development of proper life models will require consideration of debonding, matrix crack and plasticity and their effect of residual strength of the lamina.

5. CONCLUSIONS

1. Plasticity based models, such as the VFD model is adequate to model the constitutive response of $[0]_8$ lamina in tension.
2. Computational code such as METCAN is quite good in matching experimental data for $[0]_8$ and $[90]_8$ in tension. However, it does not reflect the actual deformation mechanism in the MMC.
3. Unit Cell Model using FEA is excellent in that it can capture the role of both damage and plasticity at micromechanics level on the constitutive response of the MMC such as $[90]_8$ lamina in tension and in compression.
4. In fatigue, the presence of debonding damage as a major deformation mechanism lends to a situation that Unit Cell computational micromechanics 3-D modeling may be required to model this damage mode. Life modeling may require such analyses as all current models have drawbacks to fully account for fatigue inelastic deformation mechanisms. However, 2-D generalized plane-strain Unit Cell model may be the most useful of all current available models if partial debonding can be appropriately modeled in fatigue.

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Deformation Mechanisms	Applied Lamina Strain
Nucleation of slip bands at reaction zone cracks	~ 0.004-0.005
Nucleation of slip bands at grain boundaries--onset of extensive plastic deformation	~ 0.006
Localized fiber-matrix debonding within fiber coating layers caused by reaction zone cracks	~ 0.006
Extensive slip band formation in matrix	~ 0.008
Fiber failure initiated by Mo-ribbon fracture	> 0.001

Deformation Mechanisms	Applied Lamina Strain
Onset of minimal plastic slip bands at the top and bottom of fiber	~ 0.002
Onset of partial fiber-matrix debonding	~ 0.003-0.005
Slip bands and reaction zone microcracks around 90° from loading axis	~ 0.006
Extensive fiber-matrix debonding followed by extensive matrix plasticity	> 0.006
Formation of intense shear bands between fibers leading to shear fracture	> 0.014

TABLE 3. COMPRESSIVE DEFORMATION MECHANISMS IN $[90]_8$ SCS-6/Ti 15/3 COMPOSITES	
Inelastic Deformation Mechanisms	Applied Lamina Strain
Plastic Slip Band	0.002*
Debonding	0.006-0.008
Reaction Zone Cracks	0.006
Radial Fiber Cracking	0.006-0.008
Extensive Matrix Plasticity	>0.01

* Data not retrievable at earlier strain/stress levels because of poor replica.

Figure 1. Tensile deformation mechanisms in $[0]_8$ SCS6/Ti 15-3 Lamina in the inelastic regime: slip band (sb), reaction zone crack (rzc) and debonding (db), P represents loading direction.

TABLE 4. FATIGUE DEFORMATION MECHANISMS IN $[0]_8$ LAMINA AT RT	
Cyclic Range (No. of Cycles)	Deformation Mechanism
Low Cycles (100-10,000 cycles)	Extensive <u>fiber-matrix debonding</u> and local plastic deformation followed by fiber overload fracture
Intermediate Cycles to High Cycles (> 10,000 cycles - 10^6 cycles)	<u>Fiber-matrix debonding</u> , extensive matrix crack growth and fiber fracture

Figure 2. Tensile deformation mechanisms in $[90]_8$ SCS6/Ti 15-3 lamina in the inelastic regime: extensive debonding is observed.

Figure 3. Comparison of model predictions with experimental data for the $[0]_8$ MMC at RT.

Figure 4. Comparison of model predictions with experimental data for the $[90]_8$ MMC at RT

Figure 5. Compressive deformation mechanisms in $[90]_8$ SCS6/Ti 15-3 lamina in the inelastic regime; radial fiber cracking (rfc), other mechanisms as described in Figure 1.

Figure 6. Battelle's Unit Cell computational micromechanics results for $[90]_8$ lamina at RT. Lateral constraint was modeled using springs.

Figure 7. Extensive debonding (db) in room temperature stress-controlled fatigue of $[0]_8$ SCS6/Ti 15-3 composite.

Figure 8. Comparison of fatigue behavior in metals and composites.